

against *A. flavus*, *C. sacchari* and *H. oryzae* by agar plate technique¹⁴ at three different concentrations, 1000, 100 and 10 ppm. A commercial fungicide, Blitox 50 WP was tested under similar condition to check the results. The percentage inhibition in fungus growth was expressed as :

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{(C - T) \times 100}{C}$$

where, C=diameter of fungus colony (in mm) in control after 96 h, and T=diameter of fungus colony (in mm) in the presence of test chemical after 96 h.

Results and Discussion

The compounds exhibit low to moderate level of fungicidal activity and were found to possess nearly same level of activity against the three fungi. Compounds having chlorine or methyl group in the acridine ring are more antifungal than those having unsubstituted acridine ring. A change in the position of a group in acridine ring does not show any marked effect towards fungicidal activity. The most active compounds of the series have a chlorine in acridine ring with a 4-chlorophenoxy moiety (compounds 7 and 11).

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Dihydroflavonoids from the Leaves of *Rhus insignis* (Anacardiaceae)

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ALTHOUGH a number of *Rhus* plants have already been examined for flavanoids¹⁻⁶, no work seems to have been done on *Rhus insignis*. We report here the isolation and characterisation of 3,7,3',4'-tetrahydroxyflavanone, 3,5,7,3',4'-pentahydroxyflavanone, 5,7,3',4'-tetrahydroxyflavanone, and 5,7,4'-trihydroxyflavanone, from the leaf extracts of *Rhus insignis*.

The acetone extracts of dried and powdered leaves (1.5 kg) of *Rhus insignis*, procured from Kurseong, Darjeeling (India), after purification by solvent fractionation and column chromatography (Si gel) were separated into four flavanoidic fractions (Shinoda test)⁷ by plc (Si gel-TEF, 5 : 4 : 1), and termed as RI-I (Rf 0.60, 200 mg), RI-II (Rf 0.64, 300 mg), RI-III (Rf 0.70, 150 mg) and RI-IV (Rf 0.83, 50 mg). The uv spectra of these fractions in methanol, giving only one major absorption peak at 288 nm (band-II), with an inflection at ~320 nm (band-I), and no appreciable shift of band-I in NaOAc/H₃BO₃ or AlCl₃/HCl, showed all of them to be dihydroflavonoids.

Fraction RI-I (m.p. 227-29°) showed the absorption peak of band-II at 276 nm instead of the normal peak at 288 nm. The lower value of the peak (hypsochromic shift of 12 nm) was probably due to the absence of 5-hydroxyl group⁸. The high bathochromic shift of 56 nm in band-II on the addition of NaOAc provided the evidence for the presence of hydroxyl group at C-7 of ring A⁹. RI-I on acetylation with Py-Ac₂O gave an acetate, RI-IA (m.p. 148°). The ¹H nmr spectrum showed acetoxy signals between τ 7.22-7.95 which integrated for 12 protons (four acetoxy). The doublet at τ 3.15 (*J* 2.5 Hz), a double doublet at 3.44 (*J*_{meta} 2.5 Hz) and another doublet at 2.05 (*J*_{ortho} 9 Hz) were assigned to C-8, C-6, and C-5 protons, respectively. The two doublets at τ 4.25 (*J* 11.5 Hz) and 4.70 (*J* 11.5 Hz) were assigned to C-2 and C-3 *trans* protons of ring C. The multiplet at τ 2.60 integrated for 3 protons were attributed to C-2',5',6' protons of ring B, thus establishing a 3',4'-dihydroxy system. The data were in agreement with a structure in which C-3 of a flavanone is substituted with a hydroxyl group. RI-I was thus assigned the structure as 7,3,3',4'-tetrahydroxyflavanone.

The uv absorption peaks of RI-II (m.p. 245°) in MeOH at 288 nm (band-II) with an inflection at

325 nm (band-I) and a bathochromic shift of 37 nm of band-II in NaOAc showed it to be a dihydroflavone with free 5,7-dihydroxyl groups⁸. Acetylation of RI-II by the usual method, provided an acetate RI-IIA (m.p. 140°). The ¹H nmr spectrum showed acetoxy signals at τ 7.61-7.94 which integrated for 15 protons (five acetoxy). The two *meta*-coupled doublets (J 2.5 Hz) at τ 3.08 and 3.30 were assigned to C-6 and C-8 protons of ring A. The doublets at τ 4.24 and 4.65 (J 11.5 Hz) were assigned to C-2 and C-3 *trans*-protons of the flavanone⁹. The ring B protons showed signals similar to that of RI-IA. The structure of RI-II was thus assigned to 3,5,7,3',4'-pentahydroxyflavone.

The uv spectra of RI-III were found identical to that of RI-II showing it to be a dihydroflavone with free 5,7-dihydroxyl groups. The ¹H nmr spectrum of its acetate RI-IIIA (m.p. 140-142°) showed acetoxy signals at τ 7.63-7.73 which integrated for four acetoxy groups. The signals for the C-2 proton of ring C appeared as a quartet (two doublets, J_{cis} 5 Hz, J_{trans} 11.5 Hz) at τ 4.55 by coupling with two C-3 protons. The C-3 protons coupled with each other (J 17 Hz) in addition to their interaction with the C-2 proton giving rise to a multiplet at 6.77-7.24. The other protons signals were identical to that of RI-IIA. RI-III was thus assigned as 7,5,3',4'-tetrahydroxyflavone.

Rf value, m.p. and characteristic shade in uv light indicated RI-IV to be naringenin¹⁰. The uv

spectral data were identical to the above fractions showing it to be a 5,7-dihydroxyflavone. The ¹H nmr spectrum of RI-IV was found superimposable to that of naringenin¹⁰. It was thus assigned as 5,7,4'-trihydroxyflavone.

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